

SYNTHETICAL INVESTIGATIONS ON PODOCARPIC ACID*

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The reaction between ethyl 12:6-dimethylcyclohexanone-6-carboxylate and the Grignard complex obtained from β -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-ethyl chloride furnishes 1-(β -*p*-methoxyphenylethyl)2:6-dimethyl-6-carbomethoxycyclohex-1-ene which on cyclisation followed by hydrolysis and demethylation yields 1:2-dimethyl-6-hydroxy-1:2:3:4:9:10:11:12-octahydrophenanthrene-1-carboxylic acid.

Sherwood and Short (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1006) have investigated the resin acid—podocarpic acid—isolated from the resin of *podocarpus cupressinus* (Oudemans, *Ber.*, 1873, 6, 1122; *Annalen* 1873, 170, 214) and suggested the formula (I) as the probable structure on the basis of the evidence that 6-hydroxy-1-methylphenanthrene is obtained in good yield by dehydrogenation of the acid and that the carboxyl group of it is much more highly hindered than that of the other resin acids. Recently, however, Campbell and Todd (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 928) by a series of elegant degradative reactions have conclusively proved that podocarpic acid is correctly represented by the formula (II, $R_1 = R_2 = H$).

In our attempt for the synthesis of podocarpic acid by the method which has been modelled after those of Howarth and Barker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1299), though we have been successful in building up its structure, the isolation of any of the four possible stereoisomers in the pure state remains yet to be accomplished.

p-Methoxy-phenylethyl alcohol is converted into the corresponding chloride by means of thionyl chloride and dimethylaniline. The Grignard complex, obtained from the above chloride, has been made to react with ethyl 2:6-dimethylcyclohexanone-1-one-6-carboxylate in benzene solution to yield a mixture of the unsaturated and the hydroxy compounds (III and IV) together with the product (V, $R = CH_3$) formed by Wurtz reaction. The above mixture of (III) and (IV) is dehydrated by heating with potassium hydrogen sulphate at 180° for two hours, when pure (III) is obtained. The ring-closure with usual reagents *e.g.*, anhydrous aluminium chloride, 85 per cent sulphuric acid and syrupy phosphoric acid is not at all promising. The above compound (III) when refluxed with a

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mixture of acetic and sulphuric acids for one hour, yields (II, $R_1 = C_2H_5$; $R_2 = CH_3$); refluxing for about two hours produces considerable amount of tarry matter. The above cyclised product is hydrolysed in the crude state with 20 per cent methanolic caustic potash to yield (II, $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = CH_3$). The ethyl ester of the above acid is obtained by the usual alcohol-sulphuric acid method.

In order to dehydrogenate the above octahydrophenanthrene derivative it is heated with selenium at 300° when the acid sublimes unchanged. Therefore the acid is esterified with diazomethane to give the solid methyl ester (II, $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$) whose ultra-violet absorption spectrum closely resembles that of the methoxymethyl ester of natural podocarpic acid (Sherwood and Short, *loc. cit.*). On demethylation of the acid (II, $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = CH_3$) by refluxing with a mixture of 48 per cent hydrobromic and glacial acetic acids the corresponding phenolic acid is obtained, but it does not give any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. Incidentally it may be mentioned that (V) on demethylation also fails to give the ferric chloride colouration.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 2:6-Dimethylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate.—Ethyl 2-methylcyclohexanone-2-carboxylate (60 g.) was refluxed on the water-bath for 2 hours with sodium (0.6 g.) and alcohol (45 c.c.) to yield the corresponding pimelic ester derivative (65 g.). The Dieckmann reaction with two atoms of sodium in benzene gave only a 45-50 per cent yield of the cyclic compound which was next methylated in benzene.

p-Methoxyphenylethyl alcohol.—The following method furnished a better yield than that used by Short, Plimmer and Hill (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 694).

A mixture of magnesium (13 g.), ether (50 c.c.) and methyl iodide (1 c.c.) was refluxed and when the reaction started, a solution of *p*-bromo-anisole (72 g.) in ether (200 c.c.) was dropped slowly during 5 hours; the vigour of the reaction was maintained all the time. After the reaction was complete, the solution was cooled in ice and then a cold solution of ethylene oxide (26 g.), prepared from ethylene chlorohydrin and powdered caustic potash, in benzene was dropped into the solution of the Grignard complex in two lots.

During the addition the flask was constantly shaken as the yield depended on efficient cooling. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for three days and then heated on the water-bath for 2 hours. It was worked up in the usual manner; yield over 73%.

p-Methoxyphenylethyl Chloride.—Thionyl chloride (21 c.c.) was added to a cooled solution of the above alcohol (39.5 g.) in dimethylaniline (31 g.). The solution was allowed to stand for 12 hours and then heated on the water-bath for 1 hour. It was worked up in the usual way; yield 40.5 g. The use of pyridine in place of dimethylaniline does not give any consistent result.

Mixture of unsaturated and hydroxy compounds (III and IV).—Magnesium (7 g.) was covered with ether (100 c.c.) and the ether was refluxed. A solution of methyl iodide (1 c.c.) in ether (10 c.c.) was then added when the reaction set in. After the vigour of the reaction subsided somewhat a solution of the *p*-methoxyphenylethyl chloride (12 g.) in ether (30 c.c.) was added slowly during 3½ hours. After completion of the reaction it was cooled in ice and a solution of ethyl 2 : 6-dimethylcyclohexanone-6-carboxylate (30 g.) in ether (30 c.c.) was then added to it. The reaction mixture was left overnight and heated on the water-bath to drive away most of the ether. Then benzene (25 c.c.) was added and the refluxing was continued for 1½ hours. The reaction product was decomposed with iced dilute sulphuric acid, extracted with ether and distilled, b.p. 180-200°/3 mm. [Found : C, 74.85; H, 8.6 indicating that the substance is a mixture of (III) and (IV)].

1-(β-*p*-Methoxyphenylethyl)-2 : 6-dimethyl-6-carboxycyclohex-1-ene.—The dehydration was carried out with the crude mixture of (III and IV) obtained after distilling the lower boiling fraction (b.p. 100-140°/8 mm.); The mixture of (III) and (IV) (3 g.) together with anhydrous potassium hydrogen sulphate (6 g.) was heated in an oil-bath for 2 hours at 180°. The mixture was extracted with ether and distilled, b.p. 180°/3.5 mm. yield 2 g.; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, 1.5266. (Found : C, 76.85; H, 8.54. $C_{20}H_{22}O_2$, requires C, 75.96; H, 8.88 per cent).

1 : 12-Dimethyl-6-methoxy-1 : 2 : 3 : 4 : 9 : 10 : 11 : 12-octahydrophenanthrene-1-carboxylic Acid.—The above unsaturated ester (3 g.) was boiled with a mixture of glacial acetic (27 c.c.) and sulphuric (3 c.c., *d*, 1.84) acids for 1 hour. The solution was diluted with water and the precipitated oil extracted with ether. The ether was distilled off and the residue hydrolysed with methanolic caustic potash (20 per cent, 30 c.c.) by refluxing for 30 hours. The methanol was driven away and the residue diluted with water and extracted with ether. The alkaline solution was acidified with iced dilute sulphuric acid and extracted with ether. On removal of ether, the residue was taken in acetic acid solution when after standing for 2 days crystals were deposited. The crude acid was dissolved in methanol, charcoaled and filtered, m.p. 196-7°; yield 0.01 g. (Found : C, 74.94; H, 8.08, $C_{17}H_{22}O_2$, requires C, 75.0; H, 8.33 per cent).

The above crude acid was esterified as usual and distilled, b.p. 170°/3 mm., $[\alpha]_D$, 1.5120.

1 : 12-Dimethyl-6-hydroxy-1 : 2 : 3 : 4 : 9 : 10 : 11 : 12-octahydrophenanthrene-1-carboxylic Acid.—The above acid (0.1 g.) was refluxed with a mixture of hydrobromic (48%

2 c.c.) and acetic (5 c.c.) acids for 7 hours. On cooling crystals were deposited. It was crystallised from dilute methanol, m.p. 258-60°. (Found : C, 74.1 ; H, 8.1. $C_{17}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 74.45 ; H, 8.0 per cent).

1 : 4 - Di - (p - methoxyphenyl) - butane.—The Wurtz's reaction product in the above Grignard reaction was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in plates, m.p. 83°. (Found : C, 80.48 ; H, 8.26. $C_{18}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 80.0 ; H, 8.14 per cent). It was demethylated in the above way and crystallised from methanol, m.p. 156°. (Found : C, 79.23 ; H, 7.4. $C_{16}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 79.34 ; H, 7.45 per cent).

Methyl 1 : 12-Dimethyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4 : 9 : 10 : 11 : 12-octahydrophenanthrene-1-carboxylate.—The acid (II, $R_1=H$; $R_2=CH_3$; 0.2 g.) in ethereal solution was treated with diazomethane. It was allowed to stand for 4 days. The excess of diazomethane was destroyed with acetic acid and ethereal layer was washed with dilute alkali and water. On removal of ether a solid separated which was crystallised from dilute methanol, m.p. 136-137.5°. (Found : C, 74.0 ; H, 9.1. $C_{18}H_{24}O_2$ requires C, 74.1 ; H, 9.2 per cent).

The ultraviolet absorption curve of the ester in methanol is shown below.

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